

DEVELOPMENT OF AN INTELLIGENT IRRIGATION CONTROL AND REAL-TIME MONITORING HUB

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ABSTRACT

The shortage of freshwater resources around the globe gives rise to the need for optimum usage. More water wastage can be reduced by watering based on crops' needs rather than just irrigating based on the volumetric water content of the soil. Optimizing agricultural sensor hubs has become increasingly important due to the growing demand for real-time data in precision agriculture. By developing an optimized sensor hub, we can collect accurate and timely data on soil moisture, ambient and soil temperature, and soil matrix differential pressure ambient light and use this information to make informed irrigation decisions. Implementing real-time variable rate irrigation decision-making models can help farmers reduce water consumption while improving crop yield and quality. By utilizing the data collected by the sensor hub, these models can accurately determine the optimal irrigation rate for each crop type, resulting in significant water savings and increased profitability. The sensor hub is designed for low-power consumption, high data transfer rates, and compatibility with various environments, including crop and soil types and weather patterns. The implemented machine learning algorithm analyzes and interprets sensor data, providing farmers real-time information on crop water needs and soil moisture levels. An Agrotronic tool was developed and calibrated using the measurement taken with soil moisture and air humidity, directly calculating the water balance. The optimized agricultural sensor hub effectively implements real-time variable rate irrigation decision-making models. Real-time observation of the environment allows for informed irrigation decisions that benefit the farmer and the environment. The research findings of this project will shed light on the application of technology and data-driven decision-making processes in precision agriculture, enabling farmers to make informed irrigation decisions that optimize water usage and increase crop yields.

The research was funded by HORIZON 2020 Grant Agreement No 858735: Innovative Sustainable Water Retention and Management Measures: "*WATERAGRI*".

Keywords: precision agriculture, monitoring, data assimilation, irrigation control

1. Introduction

The Scarcity of water and shortage required precise usage. The increase in the population raises the need for optimized production in agriculture. (Hop et al., 2022). The new technological era brought on the Internet of Things (IoT), sensors, and actuators that provide several solutions (Shinha, B., and Dhana, R., 2022). For an improved yield of crops, active monitoring of the irrigation system is needed, especially in areas where water is scarce. Energy efficiency is vital in agriculture to resolve the energy requirement needs of farming operations. In response to changing climate conditions, new and improved agricultural technologies can contribute to higher crop yields. Following improved advancement, instruments for automatically measuring soil properties are now available, resulting in higher crop yield quality and quantity. An intelligent irrigation system with a solar energy system provides energy from renewable energy sources (Al, Alia, et al., 2019). Many businesses and individuals have designed and developed intelligent irrigation systems that use smart innovation to reduce manual labor and irrigation time. These devices primarily measure volumetric soil moisture content with little or no regard for critical parameters. These critical parameters include the soil's field capacity, the allowable management deficit, available water at the root zone, crop requirements, and biophysical properties. These factors

can help reduce water demand and waste (Peters et al., 2003). According to root zones, considering soil moisture estimation uncertainty, an optimized interactive irrigation support system should cover the crop need and available water at different depth levels. Biophysical properties of the soil, thereby reducing further water usage, reducing excess money spent on the water, and avoiding losing water and nutrient to deep percolation by extra irrigation (Shock et al., 2012). Making it every farmer's desire to have it and changing their mindset to start investing more in the innovative system on their farm. Porosity governs soil functions such as water and air fluxes. This function is critical in the gas circle between the soil and the atmosphere, as well as in the flow and retention of water in the soil. These are vital processes for keeping aeration and water-holding capacity at an optimal level for soil organisms and crop roots (Renato et al., 2022). Plant with deeper roots has access to a much bigger area of soil as a result of a larger moisture body, in comparison to plants with shallow root (e.g., onions, peas, strawberries). Irrigating soil with more water than it can hold results in deeper percolation. Essential plant nutrients and other soluble compounds are lost along with water below the plant's root zone (Peters et al., 2013). Saturated soil gradually depletes from field capacity to a permanent wilting point. Meanwhile, crop production is not affected until it gets to the point where production drops. The point is known as the water stress depending on the Plant. Soil moisture loss below the stress point results in a significant loss in productivity (Rtroy et al., 2013) A soil moisture instrument is used to determine the moisture content of the soil. It can be either a mobile or handheld instrument, or it is fixed in place. The portable sensor can be used to measure the soil moisture in several areas, or it can be buried in the soil to get a deeper root level reading and the soil profile. Stationary fixed sensors are placed at prearranged locations and depths. These secured locations should have properties representing the entire field and the lowest moisture-holding capacity. (Nagy et al. 2021)

The aims were to develop intelligent, low-cost soil moisture sensors capable of tracking water demand and other agriculture-related observations – like root pressure or hydrometeorological factors. The results can be used in a dynamic data-assimilation framework, providing real-time modeling capabilities for spatially variable fertigation and other applications in precision agriculture. To compare and validate the efficiency of the introduced soil moisture sensor. The application of the more expensive commercial sensors does not provide significant information about soil moisture conditions. At the same time, the cheaper price tag may motivate farmers to invest in the improvement of traditional cultivation methods, allowing them to better adapt to changing climatic conditions.

2. Material and method

The design and development are combinations of hardware and software. The instrument was calibrated, and moisture readings were taken from three different types of soil samples. The measurement method emphasizes the system to solve the problem of determining the maximum amount of water that can be irrigated based on crop need before losing water to deep percolation before water stress begins to cause a reduction in crop productivity in real-time. The instrument comprises several parts, as shown in fig. 1. as a connection flow plan. The complete system diagram consists of Arduino Mega 2560 R3 microcontroller, which controls the entire process, as shown in fig. 2. The sensing units are two (2) DS18B20 soil temperature sensors 1 and 2, DHT 22 digital humidity and temperature sensors, MPX5100DP soil matrix differential pressure sensor, and two (2) improved capacitive soil moisture sensors 1 and 2, and TEMT6000 ambient light sensor. A 6W solar panel supplies the power and two (2) 3.7-V rechargeable batteries, as shown in figure 2. diagram. The pump carries out the watering, and the output unit comprises node MCU (ESP8266 Wi-Fi chip). ESP8266 12F is an open-source firmware for transmitting data via the internet of things to a web-based platform <http://agrotronicsystems.com/>.

Fig. 1. Detailed scheme of sensor connections to AT mega2560 (micro-processor)

Fig. 2. More comprehensive application of Agrotronic instrument for an intelligent decision system for irrigation.

2.1 System operation.

The flowchart in Figure 3 illustrates the system's operation. Once the system is powered on, it initializes within 2 minutes, and then the display unit indicates the soil moisture 1 and 2, temperature 1 and 2, and SMP of the soil. Suppose the Available moisture content is lower than the threshold. In that case, the threshold depends on whether the sandy or loamy switch is on or off, which will increase or decrease the available water holding capacity (AWHC) of sandy and loamy soil by 1.4 to 2.1 inches per foot, respectively, and the temperature of the soil is less than 24-degree centigrade and soil moisture potential is more significant than 33Kpa, the water pump is turned on. This situation indicates that the plants need moisture. If the moisture content is greater or equal to the threshold the pump is off, the information and data are sent to <http://agrotronicsystems.com/>.

Fig. 3. Flowchart for the working system of Agrotronic instrument.

2.2 Laboratory Experiments.

Preliminary laboratory studies were conducted at the soil physics laboratory of the Institute of Water and Environmental Management, Faculty of Agricultural, Food Science, and Environmental Management, University of Debrecen, Hungary, in February 2022. Following that, another test was performed to compare the results. It was carried out starting with collecting soil samples from a representative area. Thereafter we removed any plant material, rocks, or foreign objects from the samples. We dried the soil samples in a 105°C oven. The dried soil was placed in plastic flasks labeled samples 1, 2, and 3 that were large enough to allow the sensing area of my soil moisture sensor to be immersed without touching the sides of the container. In each container, a range of soil moisture was measured by adding 10 ml of water until the soil became saturated. In conjunction with a precise instrument of the institute (KERN DAB Electronic moisture analyzer). On an analytical balance, the dry and wet weights of the Sandy soil samples in the container were recorded. Calibration of the Agrotronic instrument was performed on three distinct soil samples, during which the sensors' repeatability and reproducibility were evaluated.. For each soil sample, the measurements were repeated ten times with both sensors.

2.3 Novel calibration to determine crop moisture need.

The electronics components were isolated and protected via a WTT tube 125°C (ø 13) and heat glue encapsulation. The novel soil-specific calibration was carried out using field capacity, biophysical properties, and temperature ($\text{alfafaAWCdept1} = \text{AWCdept1} * 0.5$, $\text{CornAWCdept1} = \text{AWCdept1} * 0.4$, $\text{potatoeAWCdept1} = \text{AWCdept1} * 0.3$) to determine different crop need. The procedure measures the VWC of soil samples at different depths using the reference method.

3. Results

An Agrotronic instrument for intelligent soil moisture measuring was successfully developed and calibrated. Figure. 4 and 5 shows the new device with its components.

Fig. 4. Agrotronic instrument for intelligent systems

Figure 5: The welcome page of the interactive support system (<http://agrotronicsystems.com/>)

Tables 1 show the summaries different measurements obtained from the experimental sensors, KERN DAB Electronic (% moisture by volume) and Agrotronic moisture (% moisture vol by my instrument) in the laboratory, and the readings were analyzed and compared with the help of Stat graphics centurion software using the simple regression of Kern Dab electronic vs Agrotronic moisture reading 1, 2, and 3 comparisons of regression lines of Kern Dab electronic versus Agrotronic moisture reading 1,2 and 3 by volume of water added and finally by calibration models of kern dab electronic versus Agrotronic moisture reading 1,2 and 3.

Table 1: shows summary statistical data from the analysis.

Soil Sample	Reading	Correlation Coefficient	Standard Error	P-Value	R-Squared	MAE	Lack-of-Fit
Sample 1	1 st	0.7673	0.1720	0.0058	58.88	0.098	0.309
	2 nd	0.8366	0.1469	0.0013	69.99	0.089	0.515
	3 rd	0.8501	0.1412	0.0009	72.27	0.094	0.353
Sample 2	1 st	0.8842	0.1252	0.0003	78.19	0.085	0.260
	2 nd	0.8884	0.1232	0.0003	78.92	0.082	0.619
	3 rd	0.9417	0.0903	0.0000	88.68	0.062	0.000
Sample 3	1 st	0.9878	0.0397	0.0000	97.55	0.028	0.000
	2 nd	0.9960	0.0230	0.0000	99.18	0.015	0.1334
	3 rd	0.9970	0.0197	0.0000	99.40	0.016	0.1763

4. Discussion

4.1 Sensor substitutability study

All volumetric water content levels and several calibration points of the soil recorded and reading 1, 2, and 3 were taken to have a more complex behavior of the Agrotronic instrument in the soil during the tests. In general, the fixed pattern in the Agrotronic moisture instrument is more pronounced. A comparison between measurements of the sensor at the same volumetric water content level was performed based on samples 1, 2, and 3 depending on the depth of the insertion and the moisture level. In terms of sensor-to-sensor substitutability, as shown in figure 6, the comparison yields a similar response from both sensors.

Figure 6. Graph of simple regression-Kern Dab electronic commercial moisture sensor versus Agrotronic moisture sensor, from sample 1, reading 1.

The Simple Regression of KERN DAB Electronic commercial sensor vs Agrotronic moisture sensor reading 1, 2, and 3 at an interval on soil samples 1, the test results confirm no significant differences between the two sensors. The P-value derived from the ANOVA table shows less than 0.05 for reading 1, 2, and 3 in soil sample 1 and also shows a statistically substantial union between KERN DAB Electronic and Agrotronic moisture at the 95.0% level of confidence. The determination coefficient (R-Square) indicates that the model as fitted explains between 58.9% and 72.27% of the KERN DAB Electronic moisture sensor variability. The correlation coefficient ranges from 0.77 to 0.85, indicating a strong link between the variables. The standard estimation error indicates that the residual deviation ranges from 0.14 to 0.17. This value can be used to construct prediction limits for new observations. Finally, the mean absolute error of 0.097 indicates that the soil moisture measurements are less than 1% off, which is practically insignificant in agriculture.

4.2 Comparison of Regression Lines.

The experimental characterization also contributed to a better understanding of how the novel sensor (Agrotronic moisture instrument) functions in comparison to a commercialized, well-controlled soil sensor.

Figure 7. Graph of Comparison model for Kern Dab electronic commercial moisture sensor versus Agrotronic moisture sensor from sample 1, reading 1.

The study demonstrated a correlation between the dependent variable: KERN DAB Electronic (% moisture by volume), Independent variable: Agrotronic moisture (reading 1 % moisture vol by my instrument). Double reciprocal mathematical model of $Y = 1/(a + b/X)$. KERN DAB Electronic versus Agrotronic moisture by Vol of water added the dependent variable as shown in Figures 7. Agrotronic moisture with level codes of the volume of water added. Several complete cases, 11 Number of regression lines, 11. 90% of the outputs show the results of matching a linear regression mathematical model to describe the connection between KERN DAB Electronic, Agrotronic moisture, and volume of water added. The P-value derived from the ANOVA table shows less than 0.05, therefore exists a statistically meaningful correlation between both variable quantities at the 95.0% certainty level.

In addition, the new innovative instrument is convenient because it is inexpensive and can serve as a substitute for the costly ones in terms of durability and efficiency. The commercially available instruments are expensive and most often complicated for the farmer to use. Current improvements in electronics have led to the development of affordable sensors that can be coupled into fully operational systems. This research study exhibits an extraordinary possibility for applications of digital technologies in cultivation/agriculture. It helps in decision-making, as shown in figures 5. where users will access web-based services of data collected on the webpage from sensors and interactive support system <http://agrotronicsystems.com/>. The strong relationship between water matric potential and plant-available water is advantageous for irrigation and hydrology control and management. Electronic devices and the Internet of Things was used to implement the automated acquisition of data for irrigation control and management. A low-cost Agrotronic system was designed based on an open-source microcontroller platform and other parts. It accomplishes precise measurements of soil matric potential at regular periods. It uses a software platform to keep data in a hard drive for future use for control and management, therefore optimizing the use of water on the farm for improved agricultural production. The intelligent instrument knows how much water in the soil depth is accessible by the plants. The rooting depth is different for various crops and their age.

5. Conclusions

The new, intelligent, low-cost soil moisture instrument was designed and developed; it can be run with digital outputs. They are three major components of the Instrument are (capacitive moisture sensor, Soil matric potential sensor, and microcontroller). The optimized, low-cost intelligent system determines the maximum volume of moisture that can be irrigated before losing water to deeper percolation. It has been demonstrated that capacitive sensors can accurately measure soil moisture at a low cost and with sufficient precision. The calibration process validated the influence of the instrument based on plant needs. Consequently, the possibility of using the calibration curve without removing the instrument from the soil and transmitting data via the internet of things to a web-based platform <http://agrotronicsystems.com/> offers flexibility and comfort. Not many commercial sensors offer this capability, and even if they do, the price will be significantly higher. Agrotronic instrument accuracy might be a little lower than a few commercial sensors. Nevertheless, the low cost is significant and acceptable. Localizing irrigation at a certain depth, temperature correction, available water holding

capacity of the soil, and soil water pressure provide more helpful information than the volumetric water content readings used by commercial sensors.

6. References

Alalia, A., A. Nabulsia., H.S. Mukhopad., A.M Shihab., S. Fernandesd, & K. Ailabouni. 2019. IoT-solar energy powered smart farm irrigation system.

Hop, Q. T., Fehér, Zs. Z., Túri N., & Rakonczai, J. (2022): Climate Change as an Environmental Threat on the Central Plains of the Carpathian Basin Based on Regional Water Balances. *Geographica Pannonica*, 26(4), pp. 194–199.

Nagy, A., Szabó, A., Farkasné Gálya, B., & Tamás, J. (2021): Real-time spectral information to measure crop water stress for variable rate irrigation scheduling. In: Stafford, J.V. (szerk.) *Precision agriculture '21*. Wageningen Academic Publishers. 427–433. eISBN: 978-90-8686-916-9, ISBN: 978-90-8686-363-1 doi: 10.3920/978-90-8686-916-9

Peters, R., K. Desta., L. Nelson., & Wsu 2013. Prosser Irrigated Agriculture Research & Extension Center.

Rakonczai, J., Ladányi Zs., Blanka, V., Fehér Zs., & Kovács, F. (2021): A globális környezeti változások fontosabb magyarországi hatásai. In: *Elfogyasztott jövőnk?* Corvinus University, Budapest, pp. 271–303. Shock, C. – E. – Jaderholm, S. (2012): A Comparison of six soil moisture Sensors. *Agricultural Experiment Station – Special Report*, 1038, pp. 262–267

Shock, C., E. Feibert., & S. Jaderholm. 2012. A Comparison of six soil moisture Sensors. Available online at: <http://www.cropinfo.net/AnnualReports/2001/Popsensortest01.htm>

Sinha, B., & Dhanalakshmi, R. (2021): Recent advancements and challenges of Internet of Things in smart agriculture: A survey, *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 126(4) DOI:10.1016/j.future.2021.08.006